

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF TIG-WELDED ALUMINIUM 7075 JOINTS: WELD APPLICATION & THERMAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract— Aluminium 7075 is a high-strength aluminium alloy primarily composed of zinc, with magnesium and copper as key elements, offering exceptional mechanical properties and corrosion resistance. Widely used in aerospace, automotive, marine, and defence industries, it stands out for its excellent strength-to-weight ratio, making it ideal for aircraft structures, automotive components, and high-performance bicycles. In aerospace, its lightweight yet high tensile strength (up to 570 MPa) enhances fuel efficiency while ensuring structural integrity. The automotive sector benefits from its durability and resistance to fatigue, making it suitable for suspension components and performance parts. Aluminium 7075 offers a significant weight reduction without compromising mechanical strength, supporting advancements in lightweight engineering and sustainability. Despite its excellent strength and lightweight properties, Aluminium 7075 has some drawbacks that limit its applications. It has poor weldability due to its high zinc content, which makes fusion welding challenging and requires special techniques like friction stir welding, TIG, MIG. An experimental setup incorporating TIG, MIG, and friction stir welding (FSW) can help determine the optimal welding method for Aluminium 7075, addressing its poor weldability. In TIG (Tungsten Inert Gas) welding, a non-consumable tungsten electrode is used with an inert gas shield, ensuring precise control over heat input, making it suitable for thin sections. MIG (Metal Inert Gas) welding, using a consumable wire electrode and shielding gas, offers higher deposition rates but requires careful heat control to prevent porosity and strength loss. FSW, a solid-state joining technique, uses a rotating tool to plastically deform and fuse the material without melting, reducing heat-affected zones and maintaining mechanical integrity. A controlled experiment comparing these methods on 7075 aluminium plates, analysing joint strength, microstructure, and defect formation, helps identify the most effective welding approach for industrial applications.

Keywords— Aluminium 7075, Poor Weldability, TIG, MIG, Friction Stir Welding.

I. INTRODUCTION

As awareness of global warming and environmental issues rises, researchers and manufacturers are seeking sustainable ways to enhance fuel efficiency. One viable solution is using lightweight materials like aluminium and magnesium alloys in transportation. Aluminium alloys are particularly appealing because they offer a strong combination of high strength-to-density ratio, tough fracture resistance, and ability to resist stress corrosion cracking. However, forming aluminium alloy panels with complex shapes at room temperature is challenging due to their low formability and low weldability. Increasing the forming temperature can improve the ductility of the alloy, allowing for the production of more complex high-strength components [3]. Aluminium 7075 is a high-strength, heat-treatable aluminium alloy that belongs to the 7xxx series, primarily known for its excellent mechanical properties and superior strength-to-weight ratio. Developed in the 1940s by Sumitomo Metal Industries for the aerospace industry, it has since been widely used in applications where high strength and durability are crucial. Sumitomo Metal Industries, a leading Japanese metallurgy and materials company, has played a significant role in the development and advancement of high-performance aluminium alloys, particularly those used in aerospace, automotive, and structural applications. One of their most notable contributions is the development of Aluminium 7075, an alloy renowned for its high strength, excellent fatigue resistance, and lightweight properties. The company

has also contributed to various aluminium alloys with enhanced characteristics tailored for specific industrial applications. Due to its exceptional tensile strength, fatigue resistance, and lightweight nature, Aluminium 7075 is a preferred choice in aerospace, automotive, marine, defence, and sporting goods industries. Welding is a complex process in terms of control of temperature fields, strains, residual stresses, formation of cracks and their propagation. Welding is a crucial metal joining process in various industries, but it's complex due to temperature fields, strains, residual stresses, and crack formation. The process generates inhomogeneous plastic deformation and residual stresses near the weld line, which can negatively impact the product's performance. Residual stress and distortion are caused by the non-uniform expansion and contraction of the metal around the weld and within the weld pool.[4]

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

[1] R. Y. Hwang, C. P. Chou, and Department of Mechanical Engineering, National Chiao Tung University, Hsinchu, Taiwan, R. O. C., "The Study on Microstructural and Mechanical Properties of Weld Heat Affected Zone Of 7075t651 Aluminium Alloy," Elsevier Science Ltd, 1998.

The welding fabrication can produce thermal cycling on the weldment. In heat affected zone (HAZ) beside to the fusion zone, different temperatures can be obtained. This would cause change of microstructure in the HAZ of aluminium alloy weldment behaviour of weld HAZ by cutting the HAZ into many small pieces or using short time isothermal heat treatment to simulate the HAZ. This may lose some information, specially near the fusion zone, because high temperature gradient occurred in this region.

[2] A. K. Padap, A. P. Yadav, P. Kumar, and N. Kumar, "Effect of aging heat treatment and uniaxial compression on thermal behaviour of 7075 aluminium alloy," Materials Today Proceedings, vol. 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.03.196. 33, pp. 5442–5447, Jan. 2020, doi:

For AA 7075, a significant increase in tensile strength was observed under specific processes, such as solution treatment followed by cryo-rolling and aging. However, there has been limited focus on improving the thermal properties of AA 7075, which are crucial for applications at higher temperatures. Therefore, the current research aims to enhance the thermal properties of AA 7075 through solution heat treatment, uniaxial compression, and artificial aging. Further analysis showed that aging at certain temperatures enhances the hardness and strength of AA 7075. X-ray diffraction confirmed the presence of certain phases critical for strength, while optical observations illustrated how processing affects microstructure. Thermal conductivity tests indicated that aging treatment improved thermal conductivity due to the formation of micro-segregations in the alloy. Similarly, the coefficient of thermal expansion increased after heat treatment, driven by residual stresses released during aging.

[3] V. M. Varghese, S. Sreenath, M. Suresh, D. Siva Kumar, Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre (VSSC), and Sree Chitra Thirunal College of Engg, "Numerical Simulation of Residual Stress in Tig-Welded Low Carbon Steel Plates," 2006.

Tungsten inert gas (TIG) welding has high potential in industries like aerospace and ship building. Distortion and residual stresses are the major causes of inaccuracy and low strength in welded structures, and are produced due to non-uniform distributions of plastic and thermal strains.

[4] S. Sreenath, V. M. Varghese, and Department of Mechanical Engineering, SCT College of Engg: Thiruvananthapuram –18, India, "Effect of weld parameters on residual stress developed during TIG welding," 2021.

Residual stresses in engineering components and structures can significantly affect fatigue behaviour during external cyclic loading. Tensile residual stresses reduce fatigue strength and corrosion resistance, while compressive residual stresses diminish the stability limit. Residual stresses can be as high as the yield strength of the material. Various finite element models have been proposed to predict temperature fields and residual stresses produced in welding.

[5] S. S. Satputaley, Y. Waware, K. Ksheersagar, Y. Jichkar, and K. Khonde, "Experimental investigation on effect of TIG welding process on chromoly 4130 and aluminium 7075-T6," *Materials Today Proceedings*, vol. 41, pp. 991–994, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2020.05.733.

Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW) or Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) uses a non-consumable tungsten electrode made of tungsten or a tungsten alloy with cerium, thorium, lanthanum or zirconium oxide improving arc stability. The electric spark through the electrode generates a plasma arc between the base metal and the electrode tip. The electric discharge is initialised with a power source having a high-frequency generator, which produces a small spark that provides the initial conducting path for the welding current through the shielding gas and allows the arc to initiate while the electrode and the base metal are separated.

[6] U. Dwivedi, S. Tiwari, A. Mishra, and Sreethul Das, "Comparative Study of Weld Characteristics of Friction Stir Welded Joints on Aluminium 7075 with Autogenous TIG," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 22, pp. 2532–2538, 2020. 3

The grain size increases with high rotational speeds which also indicate why the tensile strength decreases as the rotational speed increases. The hardness of FSW sample in the weld part came better than the hardness of the sample welded from autogenous TIG welding. Also, the hardness of the sample increases with the increase in rotational speed of the tool in FSW. FSW generates less heat during the process and hence suited to join workpieces which are difficult to weld. While the tool is moved along the joint line, it mechanically alloys the two samples of metal, and manufactures the hot and mollified metal by the mechanical pressure, which is exerted by the tool.

[7] "Fatigue Lifetime of Laser-MIG Hybrid Welded Joint of 7075-T6 Aluminium Alloy by in-situ Observation," journal-article, Aug. 2017.

7075-T6 aluminium alloy is a heat-treatable aluminium alloy with low density, moderately high strength, excellent corrosion resistance and good processing performances. Fatigue fracture surface of base metal has many dimples, while fracture surface of welded joint has many gas porosities of different sizes. For welded joint, gas porosity is the main factor affecting fatigue crack initiation, and the main reason for the decrease of the fatigue strength of welded joint of 7075-T6 aluminium alloy.

[8] A. Raj, M. Shafeek, J. V. V. M, and A. Anand, "Incremental sheet forming of dissimilar friction stir welded AA1100 and AA6061 blanks using single point tool," *Welding International*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 66–75, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1080/09507116.2024.2441943.

Friction Stir Welding (FSW) presents a promising alternative. FSW is a solid-state welding process that is particularly well-suited for softer materials and can overcome some of the challenges associated with fusion welding of aluminium alloys. The solid-state welding process known as friction stir welding (FSW) offers a solution to overcome challenges associated with fusion welding of aluminium alloys.

III.MATERIAL AND COMPOSITION

One of the defining characteristics of Aluminium 7075 is its composition, which includes a significant amount of zinc, along with magnesium, copper, and small traces of other elements. The typical chemical composition of Aluminium 7075 is as follows:

TABLE 1
COMPOSIRTION OF ALUMINIUM 7075

Composition	Weight Percentage (%)
Zinc	5.28
Magnesium	2.66
Copper	1.52

Iron	0.35
Manganese	0.092
Silicon	0.07
Chromium	0.22
Titanium	0.29
Aluminium	Balance

Fig 1: Aluminium 7075

The material tested in this study was 7075 aluminium alloy sheet with a thickness of 4mm. 7075 aluminium alloy is a commercial Al-Zn-Mg-Cu alloy. The chemical composition (wt%) of the alloy is given in TABLE 1.

This filler metal ER5356 is specifically designed for Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW or TIG) and Gas Metal Arc Welding (GMAW or MIG) of aluminium alloys. It offers excellent weldability and produces high-strength joints with good corrosion resistance, especially in marine and industrial environments. Due to the magnesium content, ER5356 also provides a brighter weld appearance, which is beneficial in applications where the aesthetics of the weld bead are important.

TABLE 2
COMPOSITION OF FILLER MATERIAL ER5356

Composition	Weight Percentage (%)
Magnesium	4.5-5.5
Manganese	0.05-0.20
Chromium	0.05-.020
Silicon	≤ 0.25
Iron	≤ 0.40
Zinc	≤ 0.10
Titanium	≤ 0.06
Aluminium	Balance

Fig 2: Filler Material ER5356

IV. SPECIMEN PREPARATION

Fig 3: Dimensions of required specimen

STEP 1:

The Aluminium 7075 alloy is cut into required dimension of 60x25x4mm using grinding machine. For getting a smooth finish we selected the grinding wheel of 80-120 grid. Initially, rough grinding removes

Fig 4: Cutting Aluminium 7075 using grinding machine

excess material using a coarse-grit wheel, followed by finish grinding with a fine-grit wheel to achieve precise tolerances. This process ensures a high-quality finish and dimensional precision suitable for aerospace, automotive, and structural applications of Aluminium 7075.

STEP 2:

After grinding Aluminium 7075 to the required dimensions, the next step is cutting using a hacksaw blade to further modify the shape as needed. Since 7075 is a high-strength aluminium alloy, using the right hacksaw blade is crucial for achieving a clean and precise cut. The workpiece is firmly clamped in a vice to minimize vibrations, and light, steady strokes are applied to avoid overheating or blade binding. After cutting, the edges are deburred using a file or abrasive pad to remove sharp edges and achieve a smooth finish. This step ensures that the final workpiece meets the required shape and dimensions while maintaining surface integrity.

Fig 5: Cutting specimen using hack-saw

STEP 3:

And now we got 3 specimens of required dimension.

Fig 6: Specimen prepared

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The workpiece is cut into required specification as mentioned below and made it suitable for welding. The specimen undergoes TIG, MIG & Friction Stir Welding for our experiment. This experiment is to conduct the strength of the different weld specimen.

A. TUNGSTEN INERT GAS (TIG):

The experimental setup for Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) welding of Aluminium 7075 involves precise control of parameters to ensure high-quality welds. The setup consists of a TIG welding machine with a direct current electrode negative (DCEN) polarity to minimize oxidation and achieve deeper penetration. A high-purity argon gas supply (typically 99.99%) is used as a shielding gas at a flow rate of 10–15 L/min to prevent contamination.

Fig 7: TIG- Welding set up

A non-consumable tungsten electrode, usually 2% thoriated or lanthanated, with a diameter of 2.4 mm, is used to generate the arc. The Aluminium 7075 workpiece, prepared with mechanical and chemical

cleaning (acetone and wire brushing), is clamped securely on a copper backing plate to aid heat dissipation and prevent burn-through. Filler material, such as ER5356 or ER4045, is manually fed to improve joint strength. The welding process is conducted at a controlled travel speed, with a current setting of 100–150A, a voltage range of 14–20V, and a frequency of around 50–100 Hz for pulsed TIG welding.

B. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE FOR TIG WELDING OF ALUMINIUM 7075

Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) welding is widely used for joining aluminium alloys due to its ability to provide high-quality welds. However, aluminium 7075 is a high-strength alloy with poor weldability due to its susceptibility to hot cracking and excessive heat input. This experiment aimed to determine the optimal welding parameters for achieving a successful weld on Aluminium 7075 using an ER5356 filler material.

I. Initial Welding Trial and Observations:

Initial Parameters Used:

- Current: 150-250 A
- Voltage: 15-20 V
- Welding Speed: 10 mm/s
- Tungsten Electrode Diameter: 2.4 mm
- Filler Material: ER5356
- Parameter Adjustments and Further Trials

Trial 1: 17 V – 150 A AC

Fig 8: Trial 1

Observations: Overheated were observed, causing plate burning. High current in AC mode caused oxidation and excessive heat input.

Trial 2: 17 V – 80 A AC

Fig 9: Trial 2

Observations: Lower current reduced overheating, but penetration was insufficient for a strong weld. Incomplete fusion was observed at the joint.

Final Trial: 17 V – 112 A DC

Fig 10: Final Trial

Observations: This setting provided good weld quality with controlled penetration. DC polarity improved heat stability, reducing oxidation and overheating. The weld formed properly without burning the plate.

C. Conclusion

- AC mode at higher currents caused overheating, while lower currents in AC resulted in lack of fusion.
- The best results were obtained with 17V - 112A in DC mode, ensuring stable arc performance and proper heat distribution.
- DC polarity helped control the heat input, reducing the risk of excessive melting and plate burning.

This experiment demonstrates the importance of parameter optimization in welding high-strength aluminium alloys like 7075.

VI. ANALYSIS OF ALUMINIUM 7075 FOR TIG-WELDING

STEP 1:

The image shows an ANSYS Workbench coupled thermal-structural analysis setup, where a Static Structural Analysis (A) is first defined with engineering data, geometry, model, setup, solution, and results. A Steady-State Thermal Analysis (B) is then added, sharing the same engineering data and geometry, with results linked to the subsequent Static Structural Analysis (C) to study thermal stresses.

Fig 11: Setup of Thermo-Structural Analysis.

STEP 2:

The properties of Aluminium 7075 are added to the Engineering data for the thermo-structural analysis.

Aluminium 7075	
Density	2810 kg/m ³
Structural	
▼ Isotropic Elasticity	
Derive from	Young's Modulus and Poisson's Ratio
Young's Modulus	71.7 Pa
Poisson's Ratio	0.33
Bulk Modulus	70.294 Pa
Shear Modulus	26.955 Pa
Tensile Ultimate Strength	572 Pa
Tensile Yield Strength	503 Pa
Thermal	
▼ Isotropic Thermal Conductivity	
Isotropic Thermal Conductivity	170 W/m·°C
Other	
▼ Melting Temperature	
Melting Temperature	556 °C

Fig 12: Property selection of Al-7075.

STEP 3:

The properties of filler material ER5356 is also added to Engineering data for the thermos-structural analysis.

TIG Filler material ER5356	
Density	2700 kg/m ³
Structural	
▼ Isotropic Elasticity	
Derive from	Young's Modulus and Poisson's Ratio
Young's Modulus	6.9e+10 Pa
Poisson's Ratio	0.33
Bulk Modulus	6.7647e+10 Pa
Shear Modulus	2.594e+10 Pa
Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	2.41e-05 1/°C
Tensile Ultimate Strength	250 Pa
Tensile Yield Strength	145 Pa
Thermal	
▼ Isotropic Thermal Conductivity	
Isotropic Thermal Conductivity	170 W/m·°C
Other	
▼ Melting Temperature	
Melting Temperature	603 °C

Fig 13: Property selection of TIG Filler Material.

STEP 4:

After the primary step the second step is to choose the specific material for the specific location since in this weld we do have to dissimilar materials, the Aluminium 7075 and the filler material (ER5356) with the specified properties assigned

Fig 14: Property selection of Al-7075 welded plate.

STEP 5:

The third step include the meshing of the element. Meshing is important to get the finite elemental property so the sizing plays an important role in meshing. Here we have given the sizing as 2 mm.

Fig 15: Meshing of welded Al-7075 plate.

STEP 6:

In static structural we have given the force as 5000N at one end in y direction and we have fixed a support at another end as constrained for UTM.

Fig 16: Application of Force and Fixed Support of welded Al-7075 plate.

STEP 7:

This step includes the selection of steady-state thermal analysis in which we have given the temperature at 3 faces and the conduction heat transfer for 23 faces, which helps to find out the thermal analysis and in the solution part we have given the temperature to get the thermal behaviour of the specimen.

Fig 17: Thermal Behaviour of welded Al-7075 plate.

STEP 8:

In this step we got the temperature behaviour of the specimen and the maximum heat is affected at the necking of the specimen as the area is getting reduced.

Fig 18: Temperature Distribution of welded Al-7075 plate.

STEP 9:

In this step it describes about the Max. Principal Stress affecting the welded region which will be the cause for the failure of the specimen. In static structural we have given the force as 5000N and we have fixed a support as constrained for UTM.

Fig 19: Maximum Principal Stress of welded Al-7075 plate.

STEP 10:

In this step we got the Max. Principal Strain that affects the body to deform and is responsible for the deformation. In static structural we have given the force as 5000N and we have fixed a support as constrained for UTM.

Fig 20: Maximum Principal Elastic Strain of welded Al-7075 plate.

STEP 11:

In this step it gives the total deformation region of the welded specimen. The maximum deformation is at the region where the force is applied and that region is highly prone to deformation. The different colour in the analysis indicated the amount of deformation.

Fig 21: Deformation of welded Al-7075 plate

STEP 12:

In this step we have changes the specimen to a single piece Aluminium 7075 to compare the strength of welded joint and the single plate. Here we have given the conditions once again for the thermal analysis of Aluminium 7075. Here the heat flux is acting on a single face and the convective heat transfer is acting on 19 faces.

Fig 22: Temperature Distribution of single Al-7075 plate.

STEP 13:

In this step it gives the Max. Principal Stress for the Aluminium 7075 and the location prone to fracture can also be noticed. In static structural we have given the force as 5000N and we have fixed a support as constrained for UTM.

Fig 23: Maximum Principal Stress of single Al-7075 plate.

STEP 14:

In this step it gives the Max. Principal Strain at the specimen and which intern gives the deformation area. In static structural we have given the force as 5000N and we have fixed a support as constrained for UTM.

Fig 24: Maximum Principal Elastic Strain of single Al-7075 plate.

STEP 15:

In this step it gives the total deformation of the body under the specified load. The maximum deformation is at the region where the force is applied and that region is highly prone to deformation. The different colour in the analysis indicated the amount of deformation.

Fig 25: Deformation of single Al-7075 plate.

VII. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Fig 26: Max. Principal STRESS [MPa] vs Force [N]

From the graph we can conclude that the welded joint is more prone to failure under high loading conditions. This may be due to the lower tensile and yield strength of the filler material ER5356 (Tensile Strength – 260 to 315 MPa, Yield Strength – 125 MPa) than the Aluminium 7075 (Tensile Strength – 560 to 700 MPa, Yield Strength – 480 to 600 MPa).

Fig 27: Max. Principal Strain vs Force [N] graph

The welded sample experiences more deformation under the same applied force, meaning it is weaker and more ductile due to welding defects (e.g., heat-affected zone softening, residual stresses, and microstructural changes). This may be due to the heat-affected zone (HAZ) lowers strength, causing higher strain. Welding defects (porosity, cracks) increase strain concentration. This may also due to the property of filler material ER5356.

The unwelded sample has a more uniform microstructure, allowing it to resist deformation better.

Fig 28: Temperature analysis of welded joint and single plate at the application of heat

The grain refinement causes the welded region to dissipate the heat. And from the graph its clear that after the melting point of the Aluminium 7075 (603 °C) the welded plates shows high dissipation as the grain boundary is getting degraded.

VIII. CONCLUSION

AC mode at higher currents caused overheating, while lower currents in AC resulted in lack of fusion. The best results were obtained with 17V - 112A in DC mode, ensuring stable arc performance and proper heat distribution. DC polarity improved heat stability, reducing oxidation and overheating. The weld formed properly without burning the plate at 17 V – 112 A DC.

Due to the lower tensile and yield strength of the filler material ER5356 (Tensile Strength – 260 to 315 MPa, Yield Strength – 125 MPa) than the Aluminium 7075 (Tensile Strength – 560 to 700 MPa, Yield Strength – 480 to 600 MPa), the principle stress where higher in welded plate.

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The grain refinement causes the welded region to dissipate the heat. And from the graph it's clear that after the melting point of the Aluminium 7075 (603 °C) the welded plates shows high dissipation as the grain boundary is getting degraded.

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